

An Open Science approach to Participatory Mapping

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Summary

Participatory Mapping is a rapidly growing field, built around the fundamental principle of encouraging the use of inclusive and democratic methods in the collection of participatory spatial data. The multidisciplinary way in which Participatory Mapping has developed over the last 30 years has however resulted in a distinctly disparate field. In this paper we argue the case for an Open Science approach to be adopted. Through conducting the first large-scale systematic review of the field, challenges unique to Participatory Mapping are identified and used to formulate a set of recommendations for an Open Science approach to Participatory Mapping.

KEYWORDS: *Open Science, PPGIS, Sketch Mapping, Mental Mapping, PRISMA Protocol*

1. Introduction

Participatory Mapping encompasses a wide range of methods used to collect and compile local, spatial, data such as Participatory GIS (PGIS), sketch mapping and mental mapping (Brown & Kyttä, 2018). Developed as a means of collating local non-expert knowledge and democratising the decision-making process, Participatory Mapping has grown in popularity over the past 30 years alongside more traditional forms of GIS (Sieber, 2006). Whilst adding value to the decision-making process and giving a voice to groups of society often marginalised or ignored, there are numerous challenges in Participatory Mapping, driven by the wide reaching and multidisciplinary nature of the field (Corbett, 2009). One way to unify the field and ensure progression in future research is through the application of the principles of Open Science. Whilst this has been already endorsed in GIS (e.g. Singleton et al., 2016) there has been no framework developed specifically for Participatory Mapping, which although certainly similar in many ways, has a number of unique elements requiring further consideration beyond the scope of traditional GIS. In order to understand how the field has (or hasn't) advanced over the last three decades, we have undertaken the first large scale systematic review of the field.

1.1. Background

Effective public participation relies on credible, transparent and accountable methods to enable a range of opinions to be heard and to link decision-makers to those the decisions will impact (Blackstock et al., 2006). The concept of Open Science has built significant momentum over the past decade as a way of improving knowledge sharing in research. It is a “disruptive phenomenon” designed to improve connectivity and openness in the conduct, design and assessment of research (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018; p.428). The key principles of Singleton et al.'s (2016)

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argument for an Open Science approach in the closely related field of GIS, are that data should be accessible; software should be open; workflows should be public; that the peer review process should require workflows; or that as many aspects of an Open framework should be adopted as possible (where restrictions may apply due to the sensitive nature of the data involved). Whilst these arguments have been made for GIS, there is currently no consideration as to how they might translate to Participatory Mapping, or whether there is a requirement for the field to become more open. Due to the nuanced and multidisciplinary nature of Participatory Mapping, it is likely that there are aspects that this pre-existing framework has not covered and would be of particular importance in the collection of participatory spatial data from the public. For example it is widely acknowledged that there is confusion and overlap in many of the terms used to define Participatory Mapping methods (e.g. Brown & Kytta, 2018), an apparent dominance of certain modes of spatial representation (e.g. Denwood et al., 2021), and no clear guidelines on reporting specific methodological details to ensure that future research can learn from what has already been done (e.g. Radil & Jiao, 2016).

1.2. Research Aims

In this paper we seek to address this gap by making the case for adopting an Open Science approach to Participatory Mapping in order to improve knowledge sharing and transparent reporting of methods. Not only does this have the potential to act as a catalyst for development in the field, but is also vitally important for building trust with those who participate and adding veracity to the data produced (Kedron et al., 2021). The need for this approach is to be demonstrated through the first, large scale systematic review of Participatory Mapping research to highlight specific areas unique to the field that would be improved by following the principles of Open Science. Systematic reviews are being used with increasing frequency to support decision-making and guide the development of policy by following a set of specific principles to minimise bias and produce high-quality, replicable results (Gholizadeh et al., 2020; Behghadami & Janati, 2019). The findings from this review will be presented as a set of recommendations for rigorous and effective reporting of Participatory Mapping research.

2. Methods

Four areas of exploration will be covered in the systematic review in order to obtain a better understanding of the suitability of the existing body of literature with the principle of Open Science:

1. How are the different methods being used/reported?
2. What details are provided on the data collected?
3. What information is being recorded on those who participate?
4. Who is the research being conducted by and where is it being published?

The systematic review will be conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analysis (PRISMA) protocol (Moher et al., 2009). The process of selecting the papers to review within the protocol is fourfold. First, papers are identified from two search engines (Scopus and Web of Science in this instance), including all dates up to the 16th June 2020. Relevant articles are identified using a precise set of key terms often used when describing the dominant methods in Participatory Mapping following Boolean logic (*“Mental Map*” OR “Sketch Map*” OR “PGIS” OR “PPGIS” OR “Participat* GIS” OR “Participat* Map*” OR “Participat* Geographi* Information” OR “Community Integrated GIS” OR “Collaborat* GIS” OR “GIS for Participat*” OR “GIS in Participat*” OR “Bottom up GIS” OR “Community GIS”*). This returned a total of 6,467 results, from which 2,197 duplicates were removed.

Second, articles that do not meet specific eligibility criteria based on the title, abstract or keywords are removed. Exclusion at this stage was made where articles were: (a) not relevant or within the scope of the research, (b) not peer reviewed journal articles, (c) not primary research with accompanying case study, or (d) not written in English. There were a number of reasons that articles that were not relevant to this review were returned in the search, namely that the acronym PGIS is used in different disciplines i.e. medicine, geology and robotics. At this stage of the process, 3,689 more articles were excluded, and 578 remained for analysis.

Due to the broad topic and consequently high number of articles, a third step was taken to select a stratified sample from the eligible articles to make analysis feasible. To do so, articles were initially grouped by method of Participatory mapping. These were categorised under the high level definitions of PGIS (digital interface), sketch mapping (non-digital but with spatial context, i.e. a base map) and mental mapping (non-digital and freeform without an underlying spatial context). Articles that did not provide sufficient detail at this juncture were grouped as 'uncategorised'. From these a reproducible, stratified random sample 20% (n=117) was drawn (<https://github.com/jonnyhuck/literature-sampling>), and representativeness confirmed using a χ^2 test. The fourth stage in the PRISMA protocol is then to read the included articles in full for onward analysis using the four, exploratory questions outlined above.

3. Results

The results from a quantitative analysis of both the 578 eligible articles and the 117 included articles will be available for presentation ahead of the conference, along with the subsequent recommendations for an Open Science approach to Participatory Mapping. The preliminary results suggest that there are significant inconsistencies in the way Participatory Mapping is being reported in academic literature impacting both the transparency and replicability of research. By following a set of clear recommendations these could be overcome and enable the field to develop beyond its current, stagnant state.

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Biographies

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